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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

We wish to announce the publication of Volume 5, Issue 2, November 2021. In this issue, papers are included from interdisciplinary areas such as economics, education, science, psychology, and political science.

It has been our great academic contribution to publish volume 5 issue 2 in November. Publishing an issue consistently is a never ending process and it can consume enormous amount of time. The success of publication lies within the reviewer's selflessness contribution of time, intelligent, knowledge that is put into the reviewing process. The JIS is always thankful to the reviewers. Moreover, the editorials have the equal contribution to managing the editorial process and until the publication is done. It is a continuous cycle of editorial process, which does not have the ending, for this contribution, the JIS is also grateful to the entire editorial members.

Our next issue will be published in May 2022 for which we invite researchers, managers, leaders, scientists, students and others for paper submission. The call for paper submission is also announced in the journal's announcement portal
<http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/announcement/>

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an online open access journal, which offers free submissions, free publication and open access to download its published research paper from the journal's website <http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/>

It is recommended that all author(s) submitting their manuscript to JIS are advised to read the author guidelines from the journal website

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Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
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Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
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Table of content

Editorial	iv
Strategies and Equilibrium in a Game with a Moral Player <i>Katarina Kostelić and Marko Turk</i>	1
An investigation of the influence of stakeholder factors affecting the success of the implementation of inclusive education in Malawi primary schools: A case study of four primary schools in Zomba district <i>Francis Lingolwe and Grames Wellington Chirwa</i>	23
A Hypothesis in Simplicity for the Mechanism that Generates Equations in the Brain <i>William L. Abler</i>	48
Coping Strategies of the Adolescents Living in Childcare Homes <i>Sujan Shrestha</i>	55
Grenada and U.S. Foreign Policy toward the Caribbean Region in the 21st Century: A Retrospective Appraisal of the 1983 Invasion <i>Victor Eno and Keith Simmonds</i>	70
Acknowledgement to reviewers <i>From the Desk of Editor-in-Chief</i>	83

